

FABRICATION OF AMINE-FUNCTIONALIZED POLY(GLYCIDYL METHACRYLATE)/GRAPHENE OXIDE CORE-SHELL MICROSPHERE

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1. Introduction

Graphene has been extensively studied as one of the most exciting materials because of its interesting properties such as electrical, optical, and mechanical properties.^{1,2} Especially, it exhibits unusual mechanical strength and electrical conductivity, which give it great potential in various technological fields such as sensors, nanocomposites, batteries, and supercapacitors.^{3,4}

Graphene oxide (GO), derived from oxidative exfoliation of graphene, has a two-dimensional nanostructure with oxygen containing functional groups which are mostly composed of epoxy, hydroxyl, carbonyl, and carboxyl groups.⁵ These functional groups enable GO sheets to be well-dispersed in common solvents as individual sheets and provide reactive or surface-active sites for further modification and fabrication, which makes GO useful in many applications.⁵⁻⁷ However, the intrinsic properties of graphene sheets are partly altered due to the incorporation of functional groups into GO sheets. Thus, reduction process is needed to remove the oxygen functional groups so that the properties can be partially restored.⁵ Usually, chemical or thermal techniques are used for the reduction of GO sheets.^{8,9}

Monodispersed particles of core-shell structures are of interest in many fields such as electronics, optics, and catalysts, since their properties can be adjusted by hybridization of different types of materials.^{10,11} Among various core-shell structures, polymers are widely adopted as a core material because the size of polymer core can be readily controlled from nanometers to micrometers with surface of various functional groups.¹² Therefore, many kinds of materials can be hybridized onto the surface of the polymer core such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), nickel, gold, etc.¹³⁻¹⁶

In this study, we demonstrate the self-assembly of GO sheets onto amine-functionalized polymer microspheres and subsequent chemical reduction of the assembled GO sheets, forming reduced graphene oxide (RGO) coated polymer microspheres with core-shell structures. After the reduction process, the electrical conductivity of core-shell microspheres is partially restored. This technique is simple and readily capable of producing large-volumes of conductive core-shell microspheres. We believe that the developed core-shell structures may find potential uses in electronic packaging and various optoelectronic devices.

2. Experimental

Materials

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. Glycidyl methacrylate (GMA), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP, $M_w \sim 40,000$), methanol, azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN), ethylenediamine (EDA), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), flake graphite, nitric acid, sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, potassium chlorate, and deionized water.

Preparation of functionalized polymer microspheres (PGMA-ed)

Dispersion polymerization of glycidyl methacrylate was carried out to synthesize uniform-sized polymer microspheres.¹⁷ GMA (40 g) and PVP (8 g) were dissolved in methanol (180 ml) with nitrogen purging. The reaction mixture was heated to 65 °C with stirring and an AIBN solution (0.4 g AIBN was pre-dissolved in 25 ml methanol) was added to the above mixture. The reaction was conducted at 65 °C for 12 h followed by washing with methanol and DI water. Then, the microspheres produced were dispersed in DI water with sonication and 30 ml of EDA was added to the dispersion to functionalize

the surface of the microspheres. The reaction was conducted for 12 h at 70 °C. The solution was then washed several times with methanol and water. Finally, the PGMA-ed microspheres were collected by centrifugation and freeze-drying.

Preparation of GO and GO dispersion

Graphite (5 g) was added to nitric acid (45 ml) and sulfuric acid (87.5 ml) mixture in ice bath. Potassium chlorate (20 g) was slowly added to the acid mixture within an hour to avoid any sudden increase in temperature with vigorous stirring. The reaction was carried out for 96 h and the mixture was diluted with cold water (2000 ml). The mixture was washed with a 5 % solution of HCl, and then washed with DI water several times. The mixture was collected and dried to obtain graphite oxide powders. A GO dispersion was prepared by sonicating a mixture of graphite oxide (50 mg) in DI water (50 ml) for 4 h. The GO dispersion was then centrifuged to remove the precipitate.

Preparation of RGO core-shell microspheres (RGO/PGMA-ed)

PGMA-ed (100 mg) was dispersed in GO dispersion (50 ml) with sonication and heated at 70 °C for several hours to form GO-coated PGMA-ed core-shell microspheres (GO/PGMA-ed).¹⁷ The GO/PGMA-ed microspheres were collected by centrifugation and washed with DI water. Then, the GO/PGMA-ed microspheres were dispersed in DI water and reduced with 0.1 M of NaBH₄ to form RGO/PGMA-ed core-shell microspheres.

Characterization

The morphology of the samples was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM 7000F) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL JEM-1010) at 80 kV. The Raman spectra of the samples were measured using a Kaiser Optical System Model RXN 1 at an excitation wavelength of 633 nm. The Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) analysis was investigated using a Bruker IFS-66/S. Scheme 1 illustrates the instrument to measure the electrical conductivity of core-shell microspheres. Microsphere samples were placed in a cylindrical tube compressed by two electrodes located at each open channel, from which the electrical resistance of the microspheres was measured, while being compressed until the volume of the sample reached

the half of its initial state. The conductivity was calculated with following equation with the dimensions in Scheme 1 as,

$$\sigma = \frac{A}{RL}$$

where R is the measured resistance, L is the distance between the electrodes, and A is the area of the electrode (πr^2 , 9.6 mm² in this study). Electrical resistance of samples was measured using a universal testing machine (UTM, LLOYD LR30K plus) and digital multimeter (Agilent U1252A).

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 represents the schematic of the synthesis route of RGO/PGMA-ed core-shell microspheres. Upon heat treatment, the epoxy groups of GO sheets react with the amine groups of the surface of the PGMA-ed microspheres forming self-assembled structures on the microsphere surface. Subsequently, the GO shells are chemically reduced by addition of aqueous NaBH₄ solution resulting in the formation of RGO/PGMA-ed core-shell microspheres.

Figure 2a shows the SEM image of the PGMA-ed microspheres. The microspheres are monodispersed with an average diameter of 2.5 μm. Figure 2b compares the FT-IR spectrum of the polymer microspheres before (PGMA) and after the functionalization (PGMA-ed). The characteristic bands of the epoxy groups at 850 and 910 cm⁻¹ are clearly seen in the spectrum of PGMA. After the functionalization, the intensity of the epoxy groups of the PGMA is greatly reduced and a broad band in the range of 3200 to 3600 cm⁻¹ in PGMA-ed spectra

Scheme 1. Schematic of the electrical resistance measurement instrument.

Figure 1. Schematic of the proposed reaction pathway of the formation of the GO/PGMA-ed and RGO/PGMA-ed core-shell microspheres.

appears, which is ascribed to the stretching vibration of the hydroxyl groups of the functionalized microspheres. In addition, the characteristic bands at 3300 and 3360 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching vibration of amine groups.¹⁸ It confirms the formation of amine groups in the polymer microspheres through amine/epoxy reaction.

In Figure 3a, SEM image shows the wrinkled and crumpled structures of thin GO sheets with a dimension of a few micrometers and with a thickness of less than 3 nm. It has been known that the thickness of single layer of GO sheet is around 1 nm.¹⁹ The GO sheets synthesized herein may well be slightly aggregated during drying process for the sample preparation. TEM image of GO sheets placed on copper grid can be seen in Figure 3b, where the brighter area corresponds to single layer of GO sheet and darker to wrinkled area of GO sheets and overlapped GO sheets.

Figure 3c compares the Raman spectrum of graphite,

Figure 2. (a) SEM image of PGMA-ed microspheres. (b) FT-IR spectrum of PGMA and PGMA-ed microspheres.

Figure 3. (a) SEM and (b) TEM images of GO sheets. (c) Raman spectrum of GO, RGO, and graphite powders. (d) FT-IR spectra of GO sheets.

GO, and RGO powders in the range of 1000 to 1800 cm^{-1} . The prominent peak of graphite at 1580 cm^{-1} corresponds to the first order scattering of the tangential stretching (E_{2g}) mode (G band), and the weak peak at 1329 cm^{-1} corresponds to the disordered structures of graphite (D band). After the oxidative exfoliation of graphite, the G band is broadened and D band is significantly increased, which is caused by the destruction of the sp^2 structures of graphite and the incorporation of functional groups forming sp^3 bonds in the carbon network.²⁰ After the reduction, the intensity ratio of D band to G band is increased, which suggests that the number of ‘graphene-like’ domains that are smaller in size than the one in graphite is increased upon the chemical reduction.¹⁹ FT-IR spectrum of GO sheets can be seen in Figure 3d. The absorption peaks at 1740 cm^{-1} and 1370 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C=O and C-O stretching vibration, respectively. The characteristic bands at 1220 cm^{-1} , 880 cm^{-1} , and 850 cm^{-1} are ascribed to the epoxy groups caused by the symmetric, asymmetric stretching, and deformation vibrations, respectively. A broad band around 3390 cm^{-1} is consequent to the O-H stretching vibration and the absorbed water molecules.^{18,21} The result confirms that the functional groups of the GO sheets

Figure 4. (a) SEM image of RGO/PGMA-ed microspheres. (b) TEM image of cross-section of RGO/PGMA-ed microspheres. (c) Electrical conductivity of GO/PGMA-ed and RGO/PGMA-ed microspheres.

are composed of hydroxyl, epoxy, and carboxyl groups.

Figure 4a shows SEM image of the RGO/PGMA-ed core-shell microspheres. The microspheres are uniform in size with roughened surface due to the attached GO sheets and they are well-distributed without any aggregation. The inset shows a magnified image of the surface of the microspheres, where we can clearly observe the wrinkled structures of RGO sheets. TEM image of cross-section of the core-shell microspheres can be seen in Figure 4b. The surface of the microspheres is fully covered with RGO sheets without any void and fractures with a thickness around 50 nm. The electrical conductivity of the core-shell microspheres before and after the reduction is measured.

In Figure 4c, the electrical conductivity of the GO/PGMA-ed microspheres does not change upon compression, since GO is electrically non-conductive. Conversely, the conductivity of RGO/PGMA-ed microspheres gradually increases

upon compression starting from 0.68 S/m. It slowly increases to 10% of volume changes, and then rapidly increases up to 4.7 S/m at 50% of volume changes. The interparticle space seems to be closely packed at 10% of volume changes and, then, the microsphere deformation takes place, which increases the surface contact in the packed microspheres. The conductivity linearly increases without any sign of noise, which implies that there is no delamination of RGO layers from the surface of the microspheres and no cracks of RGO layers.¹⁴ We expect that it is owing to the strong covalent bonding between the RGO sheets and the microspheres and the flexible nature of the RGO sheets.

4. Conclusions

Monodispersed RGO/PGMA-ed core-shell microspheres were synthesized using self-assembly of GO sheets on functionalized microspheres and subsequent in-situ chemical reduction. The core-shell microspheres are electrically conductive with a maximum conductivity of 4.7 S/m at 50% of volume changes and the conductivity increases upon compression as the microspheres are deformed. Due to the strong covalent bonding between RGO sheets and the microspheres and the flexibility of RGO sheets, the conductivity linearly increases without delamination and cracks of RGO sheets. This work provides a facile method to fabricate monodispersed core-shell microspheres with conductivity using inexpensive and abundant carbon materials, which could be used as conductive fillers for electronic packaging or antistatic devices in the future.

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